

Phytochemical investigation of *Melia azedarach* roots

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The phytochemical investigation of *Melia azedarach* roots has afforded pentadecane, cosane, glycerol 1,2,3-tris-dodec-9-enoate, isomultiflorenone, epicerin acetate, 4 α -methyl-24-ethyl-5 α -cholestan-3 β -ol and purlol. Of these, the glyceride is a hitherto unreported compound.

Melia azedarach, known as *bakain*, *drek* and *mahanim*, belongs to the Meliaceae family. It resembles neem in many respects in having the medicinal properties¹. The plant is useful for the pest control. Its leaf extract has been reported to possess analgesic properties¹. Though there are reports² on the chemical components of its roots, yet we have undertaken a reinvestigation of the same. It is pertinent to mention here that there are several reports on the root bark³ and other parts⁴ of the plant.

Roots (5 kg) of *bakain* were collected from the Landscape, H.A.U., Hisar, and the chopped material was extracted with hot methanol. Extractives were subjected to column chromatography. The elution was started with hexane. The polarity was increased slowly. Seven compounds were isolated and characterized. Spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC 300F 300 MHz NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as the internal standard; Hitachi 570 infrared spectrophotometer; and VG 705 11-250J GCMS-DS mass spectrometer.

The known compounds isolated and characterized are pentadecane⁵ (1, 15 mg), icosane⁶ (2, 20 mg), isomultiflorenone⁷ (4, 16 mg), epicerin acetate⁸ (5, 20 mg), 4 α -methyl-24-ethyl-5 α -cholestan-3 β -ol⁹ (6, 20 mg) and purlol¹⁰ (7, 25 mg). These compounds have been labelled as A, B, D, E, F and G respectively.

Compound C was obtained on elution with hexane. Its MS (M⁺ 632) proposed its molecular formula to be C₃₉H₆₈O₆. Its IR suggested the presence of a carbonyl group (1747 cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR suggested the presence of 3 \times Me groups vicinal to CH₂ groups due to a triplet at δ 0.85 (9H, *J* 7.5). A signal at δ (6H, br) suggested the presence of 3 methylene groups β to CO groups (3 \times CO-CH₂-CH₂). A quartet at δ 2.05 indicated 12 protons vicinal to a double bond (3 \times CH₂-CH₂-CH=CH-CH₂-CH₂). A triplet at δ 2.30

showed six protons α to CO group (3 \times CO-CH₂-CH₂). A multiplet for 5 protons at δ 4.30 was typical of 5 glyceryl protons present on 3 carbon atoms. A multiplet at δ 5.20 revealed the presence of 6 olefinic protons. Compound C could thus be characterized as glycerol tris-dodec-9-enoate (3) and the position of the double bond is based upon biogenetic considerations because many naturally occurring fatty acids (oleic acid, palmitoleic acid, ricinoleic acid and vernolic acid) have a double bond at a C-9 position¹². The data for the known rare metabolite isomultiflorenone⁴ has also been incorporated.

Glycerol tris-dodec-9-enoate (3) : It was crystallized from MeOH as a colourless solid (15 mg), m.p. 38–40 $^{\circ}$; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 0.85 (9H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 3 \times CH₃), 1.40 (24H, br, 12 \times CH₂), 1.60 (6H, br, 3 \times CO-CH₂-CH₂), 2.05 (6H, q, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₂-CH=CH-CH₂), 2.30 (6H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, 3 \times CO-CH₂), 4.30 (5H, m, CH-O, 2 \times CH₂-O), 5.20 (6H, m, 3 \times CH=CH); ν_{\max} (nujol) 717, 1025, 1061, 1162, 1260, 1376, 1462, 1474, 2316, 2853, 2923 cm⁻¹; *m/z* (% abundance) 632 (1.53), 604 (2.10), 576 (1.18), 548 (1.18), 546 (2.11), 520 (1.26), 478 (1.59), 450 (4.80), 422 (3.62), 394 (2.57), 338 (3.48), 295 (64.61), 277 (16.23), 125 (41.79), 111 (54.63), 97 (85.48), 83 (100).

Isomultiflorenone (4) : It crystallized from MeOH as a colourless solid (16 mg), m.p. 172–174 $^{\circ}$ (lit.¹¹ 173–175 $^{\circ}$); ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 0.92–0.98 (24H, m, 8 \times Me), 1.25–2.30 (24 H, m, 24 aliph H); ν_{\max} (nujol) 840, 1023, 1096, 1259, 1376, 1462, 1737, 2851, 2921 cm⁻¹; *m/z* 424, 396, 383, 281, 255, 191, 147, 123, 97, 71, 51 (100%).

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